

Gas Loop

Economic assessment

The economic viability of this innovation has been assessed in terms of the impact on value of kg meat produced applying the ammonia air treatment system (Figure 1).

Furthermore, in a case study costs have been assessed in case of construction of a pig barn equipped with the ammonia air treatment system and in case of building arrangement to accommodate the air treatment system in a second time.

Costs rate of kg meat produced

Related to the quotation of 2.27 €/kg for heavy pigs in the protected circuit for the PDO chain (CUN pigs, December 2023), the treatment system involves costs of 0.15 - 0.17 €/kg of live weight sold, namely an **impact of 7.3% on the sales value** (figure 1).

Ammonia air treatment system costs of a case study

- Total installation cost (treatment plus building arrangement): 208,000 € - 16.2% of total pig barn cost
- Building arrangement costs for installation afterwards: 28,000 € - 13.5% of total cost

Further details

€ **Total budget** € 189,757,14
Total financed € 176,081,45
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Costs assessment of ammonia air treatment in pig livestock for nitrogen recovery

Objectives

The objective of this OG is to generate a nitrogen virtuous cycle (loop) in the pig farming, which, producing ammonium sulphate by capturing ammonia emissions, reduces chemical inputs for the farming crops and consequently GHG emissions generated by their industrial production.

The aim is also to increase the animal welfare and productivity due to better air quality inside the pig housing (PDO heavy pig supply chain).

Figure 1. Cost items and their percentage impact on the annual management costs (productive costs increment equal to 0.16 cents per kg meat)

Case study

Società Agricola Colombaro from Formigine (Modena) has been chosen as case study.

The pig livestock was an open-cycle fattening farm to produce heavy pigs (170 kg) intended for Parma ham PDO.

One of the pig barn building should have been renovated, and the case study has estimated the new pig barn building costs with the new ammonia air treatment system.

Case study estimation Costs

- Demolition cost 90,000 €
- Total cost of construction 1,284,400 € (892 €/place - SAU animal available surface 1.16 m² /head)
- Ammonia treatment installation cost 208,000 €
- The treatment system cost 16.2% of the basic cost of the pig barn.
- The only additional works of arrangement have a cost equal to 2.2% of the base cost of the pig barn.

Main Benefits

- Reduction of ammonia emission by 54%, acidification by 21% and the formation of particulates by 17%
- Improving of indoor air quality, reducing ammonia in the treated room by 62% on average.
- Improvement in animal welfare and working conditions for staff.
- Production of an ammonium sulphate solution as liquid inorganic fertilizers allows to avoid the share of GHG due to the synthesis of industrial nitrogenous.

Context

The average ammonia emissions to air from the intensive housing for fattening pigs, when no mitigation measures are applied, is in the range 1.8 ÷ 4.9 kg NH₃ ap⁻¹yr⁻¹ (IRPP Bref, 2017).

Location in the Nutri-Know value chain

Ammonia emissions capture for a virtuous nitrogen cycle in pig livestock

Efficient and affordable solutions to reduce the ammonia emissions and, at the same time, increase the nutrient recovery, improve animal welfare and the health of workers, have to become more and more necessary in the BATs, to improve sustainability of the farming systems in the frame of the circular economy. This is particularly true in areas with high industrial and livestock intensity such as the Po Valley (where Emilia-Romagna region is located) where ammonia emissions cause problems for air quality and where ammonia is a precursor to the formation of fine particulate matter (PM 2,5 – PM 10).

The EIP-AGRI Operational Group Gas Loop has implemented (up to a Technological Maturity Level equal to TRL 8) and monitored (1 year) an air washing system that removes ammonia from the pig stables, recovering it in an ammonium sulphate solution.

An important nutrient such as nitrogen, which in the form of ammonia emitted into the atmosphere causes so many problems, can be recovered and give life to fertilizers in a view to nutrient recovery and reuse.

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